

REGULATORY MODEL OF BAITUL MAAL WAT TAMWIL (BMT) IN THE INDONESIAN LEGAL SYSTEM

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Abstract

This research is motivated by the condition that the existence of Baitul Maal wat Tamwil gives rise to normative conflicts and normative vacuums due to the existence of regulations regarding Baitul Maal wat Tamwil which are not yet focused on a single regulation, such as the Law on Banking. This study aims to answer questions regarding the nature of Baitul Maal wat Tamwil in the Indonesian Legal System, the regulation and implementation of BMT in the Indonesian Legal System, and the model for regulating BMT after the Indonesian Legal System. This research is a normative legal research using the method of Philosophical, Historical, Legislative, Conceptual, and Comparative Approach. The legal materials consist of Primary, secondary, and tertiary laws collected using library research. The results of the study indicate that the essence of BMT in the Indonesian legal system is an integrated independent business center as one of the economic system models, which is based on sharia principles in accordance with Islamic teachings in economic activities. In achieving its objectives, a new legal entity is needed, namely the BMT itself so that the unique BMT operations can be carried out. The recommendation is that BMTs must have their own regulations for operating as financial institutions, whether in the form of associations or associations. The government, both the House of Representatives and the President, should formulate specific legal norms governing the management of BMTs as Islamic microfinance institutions, as established legal entities require a legal basis for their legal regulation.

Keywords: Baitul Maal wat Tamwil, BMT, Regulatory Model.

INTRODUCTION

In the reform era, Islamic economics has increasingly strengthened its role in national economic development, particularly marked by the enactment of Law Number 21 of 2008 concerning Islamic Banking. Prior to this law's enactment, there were no laws and regulations governing Islamic Financial Institutions (LKS). The Banking Law implicitly provided an opportunity for banks to implement the profit-sharing principle in their operations. The profit-sharing principle is one of the principles recognized in Islamic economic law. It was on this basis that the first Islamic banking financial institution, Bank Muamalat Indonesia (BMI), was established in 1992, which later became the forerunner to the emergence of other Islamic Financial Institutions (LKS) in Indonesia. (Vargholy, 2018)

The establishment of Baitul Maal wat Tamwil is based on the interest of explaining the principles of Islamic economics in practice, economic principles based on monotheism, justice, equality, freedom, mutual assistance, and tolerance as well as the principles of muamalah such as kinship, mutual cooperation, taking advantage, avoiding harm and concern for the economically weak, as well as the demands and support from the Muslim community for the existence of sharia-based financial institutions, because the majority of the Indonesian population is Muslim, but there are no sharia-based financial institutions yet. In addition, the

establishment of Baitul Maal wat Tamwil in Indonesia was inspired by the issuance of Government policies based on Law Number 7 of 1992 concerning Banking and Government Regulation Number 72 concerning People's Credit Banks based on profit sharing. (Mardani, 2015)

Baitul Maal wat Tamwil is a Microfinance Institution that operates based on sharia principles. In a Baitul Maal wat Tamwil Institution there are 2 (two) financial managements in it, namely Baitul Maal and Baitul Tamwil. In terms of language, Baitul Maal is a treasure house, while Baitul Tamwil is the development of wealth, Baitul Maal financial management includes the collection and distribution of funds for zakat, infak and shadaqah (ZIS) productively from the community whose funds come from its own members or the wider community who entrust the management of their ZIS funds to Baitul Maal wat Tamwil.

Meanwhile, the concept of Baitul Tamwil is an institution that carries out productive business development activities and investments in improving the welfare of micro entrepreneurs through financing and saving activities, so that Baitul Maal wat Tamwil is a business institution in its Baitul Tamwil activities and also as a social institution in its Baitul Maal activities. Therefore, the Baitul Maal wat Tamwil serves to capture the aspirations of the Muslim community amidst concerns about usury-based economic activities, while also providing funding support for the development of small and medium-sized enterprise empowerment activities. The presence of the Islamic microfinance institution, Baitul Maal wat Tamwil, is perceived to have brought financial benefits to the unbankable community and its rejection of usury, due to its focus on a people-oriented economy.

The development of Baitul Maal wat Tamwil was not accompanied by clear regulations and legal frameworks. Baitul Maal wat Tamwil has unique characteristics compared to other existing financial institutions, because in addition to its commercial mission (Baitul Tamwil), it also has a social mission. Therefore, Baitul Maal wat Tamwil can be said to be a new type of microfinance institution compared to those that already exist. Therefore, Baitul Maal wat Tamwil takes the legal form of a cooperative, although it is still optional, not mandatory.

Since its inception until now, the legality of Baitul Maal wat Tamwil has not existed, it's just that many Baitul Maal wat Tamwil choose a cooperative legal entity, namely Law Number 25 of 1992 concerning Cooperatives which has been amended to Law Number 17 of 2017 concerning Cooperatives, so that this Law was annulled by the Constitutional Court with Decision Number: 28 / PUU-XI / 2013 because it is considered contrary to the 1945 Constitution, therefore Law Number 17 of 2017 does not have permanent legal force, so that Law Number 25 of 1992 is re-enacted, but it becomes a problem in itself and burdens Baitul Maal wat Tamwil. On the other hand, there are also Baitul Maal wat Tamwil who choose to have a Foundation legal entity.

Legally, Baitul Maal wat Tamwil is based on cooperatives, but its operational system is not much different from Sharia Banks, so the products developed in Baitul Maal wat Tamwil Law are similar to those in Sharia Banks. Meanwhile, Sharia banks have a legal basis in the form of the Law on Sharia Banking, namely Law Number 21 of 2008 concerning Sharia banking, thus

giving birth to strong legal legitimacy as its basis. Because it is a cooperative legal entity, the law of Baitul Maal wat Tamwil must comply with Law Number 25 of 1992 concerning Cooperatives, Law Number 6 of 2023 concerning the Stipulation of Government Regulations in Lieu of Law Number 2 of 2022 concerning Job Creation, Law Number 4 of 2023 concerning the Development and Strengthening of the Financial Sector, and Government Regulation Number 9 of 1995 concerning the implementation of savings and loan businesses by Cooperatives.

This is also confirmed by Ministerial Decree Number 91 of 2004 concerning Sharia Financial Services Cooperatives, Ministerial Regulation Number 8 of 2023 concerning Savings and Loan Businesses by Cooperatives. These Laws and Government Regulations, as well as Ministerial Regulations, serve as the umbrella for the establishment of Baitul Maal wat Tamwil Sharia Microfinance Institutions (LKMS).

Although it is not really appropriate because savings and loans in cooperatives are specifically intended for cooperative members only, cooperatives themselves are a form of business entity that is relatively closer to Baitul Maal wat Tamwil, but according to the Cooperative Law, the activity of collecting savings funds is limited only from its members (Article 44 of Law Number 25 of 1992). Article 44 paragraph (1) of Law Number 25 of 1992 regulates that cooperatives can collect funds and distribute them through savings and loans business activities from and for members of the cooperative concerned, or other cooperatives and/or their members.

According to Article 16 paragraph (1) of Law Number 10 of 1998, the activity of collecting funds from the public in the form of savings can only be carried out by Commercial Banks or People's Credit Banks (BPR), unless the activity is regulated by a separate Law, as also stated in Article 46 of the Law, Baitul Maal wat Tamwil should receive sanctions for running a banking business without a business license, but on the other hand, the existence of Baitul Maal wat Tamwil in Indonesia actually received support from the Government, by being launched as a national movement in 1994 by the President. The legal entity for Baitul Maal wat Tamwil to date that is possible is in the form of a Sharia Financial Services Cooperative (KJKS).

Because there is no specific legal basis for Baitul Maal wat Tamwil, currently some Baitul Maal wat Tamwil have legal status and some have not. Baitul Maal wat Tamwil that have legal status generally use the legal status of Foundations, cooperatives, and Limited Liability Companies. Meanwhile, Baitul Maal wat Tamwil that have not legal status generally use Community Self-Help Groups (KSM), and there are several Baitul Maal wat Tamwil whose legal form is unknown. (Imaniyati, 2010) Therefore, Baitul Maal wat Tamwil is grouped into several legal status models, namely Baitul Maal wat Tamwil with the legal status of a cooperative.

Baitul Maal wat Tamwil which is a cooperative legal entity in carrying out its business activities, both in the form of collecting funds and distributing them, refers to Law Number 25 of 1992 concerning Cooperatives, Government Regulation Number 9 of 1995 concerning the Implementation of Savings and Loan Business Activities by Cooperatives, Decree of the Minister of Cooperatives and Small and Medium Enterprises Number 91/Kep/M.

KUKM/IX/2004 concerning Guidelines for the Implementation of Sharia Financial Services Cooperative Business Activities, and Regulation of the Minister of Cooperatives and Small and Medium Enterprises 35.2/Per/M.KUKM/X/2007 concerning Guidelines for Standard Operational Management of Sharia Financial Services Cooperatives.

Baitul Maal wat Tamwil has the legal status of a foundation referring to Law Number 28 of 2004 concerning foundations. The use of the legal status of a foundation for *Baitul Maal wat Tamwil* is not in accordance with the *Baitul Maal wat Tamwil* guidebook issued by PINBUK. *Baitul Maal wat Tamwil* that does not yet have legal status generally uses the form of a Community Self-Help Group (KSM) or a Non-Governmental Organization (NGO), while *Baitul Maal wat Tamwil* whose legal entity is not yet known will be registered with a notary who is part of the Mosque Prosperity Council. Therefore, based on the description above, it is clear that *Baitul Maal wat Tamwil* has a conflict of norms and a void of norms due to the existence of regulations regarding *Baitul Maal wat Tamwil* that have not been focused on a single regulation, such as the Law on Banking.

DISCUSSION

1. The Nature of *Baitul Maal wat Tamwil* in the Indonesian Legal System

The essence of BMT in the Indonesian legal system is that it is an integrated independent business center as one of the models of the economic system, namely a non-bank financial institution or microfinance institution (LKM) which has three dimensions, namely regulatory function, capital function and empowerment function which are based on sharia principles in accordance with Islamic teachings in economic activities, namely:

1. The principle of monotheism, which is oriented towards devotion to Allah SWT ('ubudiyah dimension)
2. The principle of equality in economic activities regarding rights and obligations.
3. The principle of not harming or exploiting humans in various forms of business fields
4. The principle of mutual consent of both parties or the principle of mutual consent (An tradhim minkum) without any element of coercion in business transactions.
5. The principle of brotherhood in building global partnerships and solidarity as well as the principle of universal justice.
6. The principle of material business objects, in the form of goods or services that are proven to be halal
7. The principle of providing benefits or the principle of benefits that do not involve waste.
8. The principle of mutual assistance and support to build partnerships in business.
9. The principle of balance (equilibrium) between individual and societal interests with an even distribution of income and wealth.

10. Principles that do not conflict with Islamic law or the principle of not going against the law and sharia, such as:
- a. *Usury*, is an act that is prohibited in Islam, because it is not in accordance with sharia, both *riba nasi'ah* and *riba fadhil*. *Riba nasi'ah* is a conditional increase received by the lender as compensation for the postponement of debt payment, while *riba fadhil* is the excess that occurs on the sale. (Sabiq, 2010)
 - b. *Gharar*, the lack of clarity from both parties which results in injustice.
 - c. *Maysir*, contains elements of gambling which have become part of the culture as in developed countries, which results in the added value of the economy being halted and has the potential for the collection or transfer of economic resources from productive to unproductive parties.

In strengthening the objectives and functions of BMT for community empowerment, both in the context of its function as a *baitul maal* (house of wealth) for collecting and distributing funds (*infak*, *Zakat*, and *shadaqah*) and its function as *baitut tamwil* which carries out business development activities in accordance with sharia principles that do not conflict with Islamic concepts.

BMT is a *baitul maal*, (treasure house) which is a collection of the people's assets, both in the form of state income and expenditure. The management of *baitul maal* during the time of Rasulullah SAW was the management of the people's assets by the state by ensuring that the management took an adequate portion of the *ghanimah* assets (spoils of war). In the development of the Abbasid and Umayyad dynasties, *baitul maal* has become an important institution for the state starting from collecting *zakat*, *ghanimah kharaj*, to building nets, paying soldiers and state officials as well as building social facilities. (Hisyam, 2016)

Baitul Maal in Indonesia is now becoming narrower, no longer carrying out the broad tasks that were previously carried out by the government or state as during the caliphate. BMT is more interpreted as a social institution to distribute *zakat*, *infaq*, *sadaqah* or as an *amil* institution only, with its implementers not only the government but also the private sector can do it, the implementation of *baitul maal* by the government under the name BAZIS (Badan Amil Zakat Infak Sedekah), then *baitul maal* was developed with its completeness as *baitul tamwil*. Driven by the awareness of the need to improve the people's economy, it is felt that the existence of *baitul maal* needs to be expanded its function not only as a social institution that only distributes *zakat*, *infaq* and alms but also developed as capital for the people to carry out business activities so as to improve the economic conditions of the people.

Institutionally, BMT is assisted and supported by the Small Business Incubation Center (PINBUK), while PINBUK itself must obtain recognition from Bank Indonesia as a Community Development Institution (LPSM) that supports the Bank Relationship Project program with KSM managed by Bank Indonesia (PHBK-BI). PINBUK as a primary institution that develops a broader mission, namely to incubate small businesses including BMT, the existence of BMT is a representation of community life that is able to accommodate the

economic interests of the community, namely by providing guidance and providing funding based on sharia principles. Therefore, BMT has a very important task in carrying out the Islamic mission in all aspects of life, so that all economic activities carried out cannot be separated from spiritual values, especially tauhid, so that BMT is able to accommodate the economic interests of the community. (Rahardjo, 2008)

Based on Law Number 1 of 2013 concerning Microfinance Institutions. BMTs that are not yet legally incorporated generally use Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) or Self-Help Groups (KSM) by obtaining an operational certificate from PINBUK. In Indonesia, BMTs have various legal entities, namely, foundations based on Law Number 28 of 2004, Cooperatives based on Law Number 25 of 1992 concerning Cooperatives, and Limited Liability Companies (PT), based on Law Number 40 of 2007, therefore, the three legal umbrellas above do not match the characteristics of BMTs, so BMTs need to have their own regulations, as with other institutions.

2. BMT Regulation in the Legal System in Indonesia

a. Legal Regulations of Baitul Maal Wattamwil in Indonesia

1. Law Number 25 of 1992

- a. Article 44 Paragraph (1), the definition of cooperative members as referred to in letter a of this paragraph includes prospective members who meet the requirements. In the explanation of Article 17 paragraph (1), however, as long as it does not harm its interests, cooperatives can also provide services to non-members according to the nature and activities of their business, with the aim of attracting non-members to become cooperative members.
- b. Article 18 paragraph (1) states that every Indonesian citizen who is capable of carrying out legal actions can become a cooperative member.
- c. Article 9, Cooperatives (including Savings and Loan Cooperatives) whose deed of establishment has been approved by the government shall obtain the status of a Legal Entity.

2. Law Number 38 of 1999, concerning the management of zakat in Article 13 Jo 15, receipt of zakat, infak and sadaqah.

3. Law Number 10 of 1998, Article 1 number 13, Sharia principles are rules of agreement based on Islamic law between banks and other parties for the storage of funds and/or financing of business activities or other activities that are stated to be in accordance with Sharia, including financing based on the principle of results (mudharabah), financing based on capital participation (musharakah), the principle of buying and selling goods to obtain profits (murabahah) or financing of capital goods based on the principle of pure rental without options (ijarah) or with the option of transferring ownership rights to goods rented from the bank by another party (ijarah wal itiqna).

4. Law No. 1 of 1995, Article 48-52, Transfer of shares by shareholders to other parties,

5. Law Number 7 of 2007 concerning Religious Courts, the resolution of sharia business disputes can be resolved in religious courts.
6. Civil Code
 - a. Article 1320, Terms of validity of an agreement
 - b. Articles 1618-1652, Mudharabah term has many similarities with deposit agreements.
 - c. Article 1243, compensation for costs, losses and interest due to failure to fulfill an obligation begins to be required if the debtor, even though he has been declared negligent, continues to be negligent in fulfilling the obligation, or if something that must be given or done can only be given or done within a time that exceeds the time that has been determined.
7. Commercial Code (KUHD), Articles 19-21, Limited Partnership (Commanditaire vennootschap or CV)
8. Government Regulation Number 9 of 1995
 - a. Article 1 number 1, Savings and loan business activities are activities carried out to collect funds and distribute them through savings and loan business activities from and for members of the cooperative concerned, prospective members of the cooperative concerned, other cooperatives and/or their members.
 - b. Article 1 paragraph (4), savings are funds entrusted by members, prospective members, other cooperatives and/or their members to the cooperative.
 - c. Article 19 paragraph (1), Savings and loan cooperatives (and savings and loan business units) can collect funds in two forms of savings, namely cooperative savings and term deposits.
 - d. Article 2 paragraph (1), savings and loan business activities can only be carried out by savings and loan cooperatives (KSP) or savings and loan units (USP) which have obtained legal entity status.
9. Presidential Decree Number 61 of 1998 concerning Financing Institutions, divesting, transferring shares, or divestment.
10. Decree of the Minister of Religion of the Republic of Indonesia Number 581 of 1999
 - a. Article 27, Receipt of zakat, infak and sadaqah
 - b. Article 28, paragraph (1), the utilization of the results of zakat collection for mustahiq is carried out based on the following requirements:
 - a. The results of data collection and research into the truth of the eight asnaf mustahik, namely the poor, needy, amil, converts, riqab, gharim, sabillah, and ibnu sabil
 - b. Prioritize those who are least able to meet their basic economic needs and are in greatest need of assistance.

- c. Prioritize mustahiq in their respective regions.
 - c. Article 28 paragraph (2), the utilization of zakat collection results for productive businesses is carried out based on the following requirements:
 - a. If the utilization of zakat as referred to in paragraph (1) has been fulfilled and it turns out that there is still a surplus
 - b. There are real businesses that have a profitable chance of getting approval.
11. Decree of the Minister of Cooperatives and Small and Medium Enterprises of the Republic of Indonesia Number 91/Kep/M.KUKM/IX/2004 concerning Guidelines for the Implementation of Sharia Financial Services Cooperative Business Activities. The matters regulated in this decree are:
 - a. Sharia Financial Services Cooperative (KJKS), according to this decision, a sharia financial services cooperative is a cooperative whose business activities are in the field of investment financing and savings in accordance with a profit sharing pattern (sharia)
 - b. The Sharia Financial Services Unit (UJKS) is a cooperative unit that operates in the field of financing, investment and savings in accordance with a profit-sharing (sharia) pattern as part of the cooperative concerned.
 - c. The objectives of developing KJKS according to Article 2 are:
 - a) Improving economic empowerment programs, especially among micro, small, medium enterprises and cooperatives through the sharia system.
 - b) Encouraging sharia economic life in micro, small and medium business activities in particular and the Indonesian economy in general.
 - c) Increase the enthusiasm and participation of community members in KJKS activities.
12. BMT in the Joint Decree of the Minister of Finance, Minister of Home Affairs, Minister of State for Cooperatives and Small and Medium Enterprises, Governor of Bank Indonesia Number 351.1/KMK.010/2009, Number 900-639A of 2009, Number 01/SKB/M.KUKM/IX/2009, Number 11/43A/Kep.GBI/2009 Concerning the Development Strategy of Microfinance Institutions.
13. BMT in the Regulation of the Minister of Cooperatives and Small and Medium Enterprises of the Republic of Indonesia Number 11/per/M.KUKM/XII/2017 concerning the Implementation of Sharia Savings, Loans and Financing Businesses by Cooperatives
14. Fatwa of the National Sharia Council
 - a. Number 02/DSN-MUI/IV/2000 concerning Savings (Wa'diah), regarding savings (wa'diah) there is no required reward, except in the form of a voluntary gift ('athaya) from the bank. Deposits can be withdrawn at any time (on call) or by agreement.

- b. Number 04/DSN-MUI/IV/2000, Concerning Deposits, savings and term deposits which withdrawals can only be made at certain times based on an agreement between the depositing customer and the bank.
- c. Number 04/DSN-MUI/IV/2000, Concerning Murabahah Financing (Qiradh) of goods which are prohibited from being traded and goods which are prohibited by Islamic sharia.
- d. Number 04/DSN-MUI/IV/2000, concerning Musyarakah Financing, contains provisions regarding the rights of financing recipients to a certain portion of the profits obtained.

15. BMT in Law Number 23 of 2011 concerning Zakat Management.

The operation of BMT carries out two financial managements simultaneously, namely baitul maal which includes collecting and distributing zakat, infaq, and shadaqah funds, and baitul tamwil carries out productive business development activities and investments in improving the welfare of micro entrepreneurs through financing and saving activities. Based on the Law, the institutions authorized to carry out zakat management tasks nationally are the National Zakat Agency (BAZNAS), Provincial Baznas, Regency/City Baznas, and Zakat Amil Institutions (LAZ), not BMT, however in this case BMT includes itself as a Zakat Collection Unit (UPZ) in order to have a legal basis for managing zakat. Zakat management by the government can have an impact on the decline in BMT financial baitul maal management activities.

16. BMT and Law Number 21 of 2011 concerning the Financial Services Authority.

Microfinance Institutions (MFIs), including BMTs, are required to obtain a permit from the Financial Services Authority (OJK). In this case, the OJK acts as a regulator of BMT MFIs. It is important for BMTs to understand the authority and scope of OJK's overall supervision. BMTs that have transformed into cooperatives, PTs, or banks are subject to the respective laws governing these legal entities. Regarding BMT legal entities, based on the MFI Law, the legal entity forms in Article 5 are cooperatives or limited liability companies (PT). Even Article 27 of the MFI Law stipulates that MFIs are required to transform into banks if the MFI conducts business activities beyond one district/city where the MFI is domiciled, or if the MFI has met the requirements stipulated in the Financial Services Authority (OJK) regulations. Therefore, the laws relating to BMT legal entities are Law Number 25 of 1992 concerning Cooperatives, Law Number 40 of 2007 concerning Limited Liability Companies, and Law Number 21 of 2008 concerning Sharia Banking.

The institutional status of BMT as a Sharia Financial Services Cooperative (KJKS) which is subject to Law No. 25 of 1992 concerning Cooperatives and has been amended to Law No. 17 of 2012 concerning Cooperatives which has subsequently been annulled by the Constitutional Court and returned to the old law, namely Law No. 25 of 1992 concerning Cooperatives, is still unable to accommodate the existence of BMT as a financial institution that serves the needs of the community. This is because BMT is different from other types of cooperatives in general,

because BMT is implemented with sharia principles that are different from conventional cooperatives and in BMT there is a social mission as Baitul Maal which cannot be forced to fully comply with cooperative law.

The BMT institution has actually been accommodated by the new cooperative law, namely Law No. 17 of 2012 concerning Cooperatives, where this law states that cooperative management uses sharia principles, as regulated in Article 87 Paragraph (3), that "Cooperatives can run businesses based on sharia economic principles", furthermore in Article 87 Paragraph (4), that "Provisions regarding Cooperatives based on sharia economic principles as referred to in paragraph (3) are regulated by Government Regulation".

The government regulation that subsequently regulates BMT is the Decree of the Minister of Cooperatives and Small and Medium Enterprises Number 91/Kep/M.KUKM/IX/2004 concerning Guidelines for the Implementation of Sharia Financial Services Cooperative Business Activities, Regulation of the Minister of Cooperatives and Small and Medium Enterprises 35.2/Per/M.KUKM/X/2007 concerning Guidelines for Standard Operational Management of Sharia Financial Services Cooperatives. And the Regulation of the Minister of State for Cooperatives and Small and Medium Enterprises 39/Per/M.KUKM/XII/2007 concerning Guidelines for Supervision of Sharia Financial Services Cooperatives and Cooperative Sharia Financial Services Units.

With the annulment of Law No. 17 of 2012 concerning Cooperatives, the regulation of cooperatives based on sharia principles was abolished and returned to Law No. 25 of 1992 concerning Cooperatives which did not regulate cooperatives based on sharia principles at all.

However, according to the Director of the Baitut Tamwil Tamzis Wonosobo Sharia Financial Services Cooperative, "now we no longer have regulations equivalent to laws that can regulate the existence of BMT, because Law No. 17 of 2012 concerning Cooperatives which specifically regulated the use of sharia principles in the implementation of cooperatives has been annulled and returned to the old law which has not kept up with the development of community needs and has not accommodated the specifications of BMT as a cooperative with sharia principles." (Masyithoh, 2014)

Supervision in BMTs that are incorporated as Sharia Financial Services Cooperatives (KJKS) is subject to the Regulation of the Minister of Cooperatives and SMEs Number 39/Per/M.KUKM/XII/2007 concerning Guidelines for Supervision of Sharia Financial Services Cooperatives and Cooperative Sharia Financial Services Units. Supervision of BMTs that are incorporated as cooperatives is carried out by the Ministry of Cooperatives and SMEs where the BMT is domiciled, if at the city level it is carried out by the City/Regency Cooperative and SME Office, while if at the provincial level, it is carried out by the Provincial Cooperative and SME Office.

3. Legal Construction of BMT Regulations in the Indonesian Legal System.

The legal construction in the regulation of Baitul Maal wat Tamwil (BMT) in Indonesia as a step towards legal certainty and strengthening so that the implications of the study of BMT and

its legal concept are more focused in carrying out its business activities as a sharia financial institution, namely forming a legal entity of the BMT association and forming special legislation for BMT management, because the legal entity formed requires legislation as its legal norm, in this context it is necessary to study in several theoretical frameworks as a basis for the author to develop research concepts and what things have been used to strengthen the BMT institution in finding legal rules that will be used in the future.

As a basis for developing the concept of strengthening BMT law, the author will examine the efforts that have been made to make BMT independent, professional and transparent, namely:

a. BMT is given a special unit within a business entity

The legal status of BMT within financial institutions is that it is a non-bank Islamic microfinance institution. The previous description explained that BMT's legal entity status is divided into two: non-legal entities and non-legal entities. To ensure legal certainty and ensure the operational integrity of BMTs in accordance with Islamic principles, BMTs are specifically designed to be established as a special, autonomous unit within a legal entity.

b. The Establishment of a Special BMT Institution

BMTs have various associations or associations, namely the Indonesian BMT Association (PBMT Indonesia), the BMT Sharia Cooperative Parent (Inkopsyah BMT), and the Indonesian BMT Association (Absindo). In the absence of a dedicated BMT institution that is independent, professional, and transparent, BMT associations have taken over the functions of these institutions with the aim of overseeing, developing, and coordinating the potential of BMTs within a solid network.

c. Consistency of the Scope of Microeconomics

The philosophical basis for the need for a legal entity and the formulation of legal norms regarding BMT in Indonesia as a legal strengthening of people's economic institutions is essentially for the sake of legal certainty that can provide recognition, protection, and facilities for the development and benefits of the existence of BMT for micro and small entrepreneurs who do not have access to banking services. The change in the legal status of BMT to become a BPRS as a micro bank, is expected to remain based on the philosophical basis of the existing regulations for MFIs.

The legal concept of BMT in Indonesia to be applicable to economic actors can be realized in the form of written law and will be effective if its substance is in accordance with the values of Pancasila philosophy, good law is there is a conformity between the legal form regulated with the content regulated in the law. The philosophical implication expected by BMT in Indonesia is the conformity between the form of legal entity with the characteristics of BMT which includes financial management of baitul maal namely the collection and distribution of zakat, infak and shadaqah (ZIS) funds from the community and baitut tamwil which carry out productive business activities in improving the welfare of micro entrepreneurs according to Islamic principles.

The underlying legal concept for BMT financial institutions in civil law is the principle of freedom of contract according to Article 1338 paragraph (1) of the Civil Code which states that all contracts made legally apply as laws for those who make them. Everyone can freely make agreements, provided that they do not violate public order or morality. (Subekti, 1985) The implementation of the principle of freedom of contract in the legal concept of BMT is the principle of suitability and the principle of dynamism.

In achieving its objectives, the management of BMT cannot be handed over to an existing legal entity, a new legal entity is needed, namely the BMT itself so that the unique operations of BMT can be carried out, without having to use another legal entity with different operational principles. So the author recommends BMT into a legal entity of an association or association either in the Sharia Cooperative association, such as Sharia Banking, so that BMT can be defined as an association or legal entity formed voluntarily by people who intend to strengthen their economic position (*baitut tamwil*) and manage social problems (*baitul maal*) in accordance with BMT which has economic characteristics based on sharia principles.

Meanwhile, the essence of the principle of dynamism is that legal change always aims to provide protection to legal subjects through legal instruments, both preventive and repressive, both written and unwritten. In other words, the law can provide justice, order, certainty, peace, and benefit for all human interests in society.

The legal model of BMT in non-bank Islamic microfinance institutions is as an economic actor that was born and operates using contracts that refer to Islamic economics. The development of Islamic financial institutions in Indonesia, especially BMT, is not followed by legal regulations that do not match the characteristics that are typical of BMT that carry out *baitul maal* and *baitut tamwil* activities, therefore new regulations are needed for BMT itself, so that BMT operations can be carried out without having to use other legal entities whose operational principles are different, so the author recommends that BMT have its own legal regulations like banking which has clear legal regulations, so that BMT in the future can be more independent and professional in carrying out its business activities in accordance with Islamic principles.

The rationale for establishing a legal entity for BMT stems from the diverse legal status of BMT financial institutions. BMT legal status is divided into two categories: BMTs that are not yet legally incorporated, and BMTs that have various legal entities, including KSPPS, Foundations, PTs, and BPRSs. None of these align with BMTs. Although cooperatives approach the characteristics of BMTs, not all of them are met according to BMT management.

This is like in the storage and distribution of financing funds must be to members and may not be outside members in accordance with the Cooperative Law number 25 of 1992. The difference in operational management of fund collection in BMT and cooperatives, causes BMT to be considered contrary to the legality of BMT as a cooperative which is not permitted to collect funds from the general public, apart from being contrary to the Cooperative Law, activities collecting public funds without permission from Bank Indonesia, can be considered to have violated Article 46 paragraph (1 and 2) Jo Article 16 paragraph (1) of Law Number 10 of 1998 concerning amendments to Law number 7 of 1992 concerning banking, "every party

that carries out activities to collect funds from the public in the form of savings must first obtain a business license as a general bank or BPR from the Head of Bank Indonesia. For the sake of legal certainty regarding the existence of BMT as a legal subject in carrying out legal acts, it is deemed necessary to strengthen BMT law by forming a legal entity of BMT association along with its legal instruments, because in theory BMT cannot be classified into existing legal entity forms and requires special legislation that regulates BMT in accordance with the characteristics of BMT.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

1. Conclusions

- a. Based on the philosophy of the need for a legal entity and the formulation of legal norms for BMT in Indonesia as a legal concept for community economic institutions is for legal certainty that can provide recognition, protection, and facilities for the development and benefits of the existence of BMT for communities that carry out micro and small business activities, the main elements of the legal concept for BMT are the legal principles, namely strengthening BMT, namely the principle of democracy, the principle of freedom of association, assembly, and opinion, the principle of legal certainty, the principle of benefit, the principle of justice, and the principle of balance.
- b. The legal status of BMT in financial institutions in Indonesia is divided into two stages according to the amount of assets owned, namely BMT which has a different legal status, causing BMT to be subject to various and partial laws, First BMT which does not have a legal entity is part of the Mosque Prosperity Council, namely using a Non-Governmental Organization (NGO) or Self-Help Group (KSM) by obtaining an operational certificate from PINBUK, where the founding assets are smaller, namely below IDR 100,000,000.00 (one hundred million rupiah), Second BMT which has a legal entity such as: Foundation, cooperative and Limited Liability Company (PT).
- c. The legal concept of BMT regulation in Indonesia in the future is the formation of a legal entity of BMT association in the form of BMT Sharia Cooperative which has its own legal regulations such as banking which has regulations of the Banking Law, so that BMT is more independent, professional, not dependent on other regulations as it is now, however BMT does not lose its initial concept which is based on sharia principles for the benefit of its members and the micro, small and medium community, so that BMT can be defined as an association with a legal entity that strengthens the economic position of both baitut tamwil and baitul maal. So that it can provide legitimacy and eliminate various changes or transformations in the legal status of BMT which give rise to a juridical consequence namely that all regulations in BMT must refer to statutory regulations in accordance with the chosen legal entity.

2. Suggestions

The Directorate General of Legislation of the Ministry of Law and Human Rights as part of the Indonesian government and policy maker in the effort to regulate the ratification of legal

entities, especially legal entities of associations or associations, to form a BMT legal entity that is adjusted to the characteristics of BMT which includes financial management of baitul maal, namely the collection and distribution of ZIS funds (Zakat, Infak and Shadaqah) from the community, and baitut tamwil which carries out productive business activities and investments in improving the welfare of its members and the community, especially from micro, small and medium entrepreneurs in accordance with Islamic principles. It is recommended to the House of Representatives of the Republic of Indonesia together with the President of the Republic of Indonesia to formulate legal norms and the formation of special legislation for the management of BMT as a sharia microfinance institution, because the legal entity that has been formed requires legislation as its legal regulation.

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